

Does Developmental Coursework Impact Successful Outcomes at Community College?

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Abstract

The mission of Onward We Learn is to prepare and inspire young people in the state to become the first in their families to attend and complete college. As both a college access and college success program, it is imperative that Onward We Learn recognize what course-taking trends in high school and early college are aligned to a student's success when it comes to college persistence and completion. We hypothesize that developmental coursework taken while attending community college is predictive of unsuccessful outcomes when it comes to college persistence and student's achieving satisfactory academic progress. Contingency table analysis was conducted using logistic regression. We observed that state community college students that needed to complete developmental coursework did not have a successful outcome, which is defined as overall persistence and/or two- or four-year degree completion. With 106 out of 315 (23%) Onward 2021 high school graduates immediately enrolled at the state community college, these results will provide useful information and interventions in ongoing efforts to increase the numbers of low-income and first-generation students who successfully enroll in and complete college.

Key Words: Logistic Regression, Estimated Odds, Chi-squared Tests of Independence, Postsecondary Completion, College Persistence, Community College

1. Introduction

Onward We Learn, founded in 1989, is Rhode Island's most comprehensive college access program. Our mission is to inspire and prepare young people in Rhode Island to become the first in their family to attend and complete college. We invest in long-term relationships with our students and families, building trust and achieving mutual respect that translates into success and lasting impact.

Onward We Learn prepares students for postsecondary education, from middle school all the way through their early years of college. Every year, we provide college readiness programs and personalized advisory services to over 4,200 middle school, high school and college students from Providence, Pawtucket, Central Falls, Woonsocket, Cranston, and West Warwick. All our students are low-income (based on free/reduced price lunch status at the time of enrollment), 95% identify as students of color, and approximately 93% are first-generation students.

We put students at the center of our model, and design and implement programming to engage them and meet their continually evolving needs. These services include personalized support through 29 advisors who operate in 43 middle schools and high schools and at the state's three public colleges. We also provide over 100 innovative programs to meet students' academic, social and emotional development, career education, and college readiness needs.

Onward's program design served as a model in 1997 for the U.S. Department of Education's Gaining Early Awareness and Readiness for Undergraduate Programs (GEAR UP) initiative. As the federal government's largest investment in college access, GEAR UP currently serves over 700,000 students in 44 states. Onward

We Learn has designed, administered, and implemented Rhode Island GEAR UP program since its inception in 1999, which provides \$3.5 million annually and has rigorous program and reporting requirements. Postsecondary metrics for the GEAR UP program include increasing immediate enrollment and persistence, and reducing the number of students who are placed in developmental courses.

The national literature demonstrates that developmental education is costly and not very effective. Students following high school graduation and prior to postsecondary enrollment are asked to take a skills assessment in math, writing, and reading. Based on these assessments, students are categorized as “college ready” or “developmental” students. Many students are then referred to multiple levels of remediation leading to successful navigation of multiple semesters before being prepared for their first college-level course. Many students are discouraged by the delay in their progress through college. (Bailey and Cho, 2010) As Rhode Island’s most comprehensive college access and success program, examining the relationship between developmental coursework and successful outcomes at community college is now a major focus of our work.

2. Purpose of Study

The work of Thomas Bailey, et. al. (2009, 2010) suggests that, on average, developmental education is not very effective in overcoming student weaknesses. Research shows that many students referred to developmental education do not go on to complete college-level courses resulting in students getting frustrated with the time and money spent. Less than one quarter of community college students who enroll in developmental education complete a degree or certificate within eight years of enrollment in college (CCRC, 2010)

The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between the number of developmental courses needed and successful outcomes at the local community college, which is defined as overall persistence and/or two- or four-year degree completion. We hypothesize that the number of developmental courses needed while attending community college is predictive of successful outcomes when it comes to college persistence and student's achieving satisfactory academic progress. With 106 out of 315 (23%) Onward 2021 high school graduates immediately enrolled at the state community college, these results will provide useful information and interventions in ongoing efforts to increase the number of successful outcomes of these students.

3. Data and Methods

3.1 Student Demographics

The sample consisted of 300 local community college students from the 2017-2020 fall cohorts. Students included in the cohort completed a Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA) form allowing Onward to obtain the student's education records maintained by the school. The enrollment management data was collected for a period of three years.

Onward community college students are low-income (based on free/reduced price lunch status at the time of enrollment at Onward We Learn) and 95% identify as students of color, and approximately 93% are first-generation students. Tables 1 through 3 summarize the sample demographics by sex, race/ethnicity, and first-generation status.

Table 1: Breakdown of program participants by sex.

Sex	Number of Students	Percent (%)
Female	153	51.00

Male	146	48.67
Unknown	1	0.33
Total	300	100.00

Table 2: Breakdown of program participants by race/ethnicity. Program participants who identified as Hispanic or Latino were removed from the other categories in order not to be counted twice in the analysis. All other categories are non-Hispanic or Latino.

Race/Ethnicity	Number of Students	Percent (%)
American Indian/Alaska Native	3	1.00
Asian	8	2.67
Black or African American	56	18.67
Hispanic or Latino	178	59.33
Other	6	2.00
Two or More Races	17	5.67
Unknown	14	4.67
White	18	6.00
Total	300	100.00

Table 3: Breakdown of program participants by first-generation status. First-generation college student, which for Rhode Island GEAR UP, is defined as "no parent living in the household has a four-year college degree from any US state."

First-generation	Number of Students	Percent (%)
No	86	28.67
Yes	214	71.33
Total	300	100.00

3.2 Developmental Course Placement

Onward students accepted at the local community college are required to take the ACCUPLACER. This is a series of placement tests that evaluate students' skills in reading, writing, and math to help colleges place them in courses that best match their skills and get them ready to take college-level courses. Developmental course placement was based on performance scores. The mathematics portion of the ACCUPLACER consists of three levels of math: arithmetic, elementary algebra, and college math. Students that placed out of arithmetic and elementary algebra were exempt from taking developmental math. Students that scored below 250 on the writing portion were placed into one of four developmental writing courses. Students that scored 247 or higher on the reading portion were exempt from reading developmental courses. Table 4 summarizes the number of students that had to take developmental coursework in math, reading, and writing. Table 5 displays the descriptive statistics of the students' ACCUPLACER scores. Table 6 summarizes the number of developmental courses needed by the students.

Table 4: Breakdown of program participants by the type of developmental course(s) needed. Data includes duplication of students for each area.

	Number of Math Students	Percent (%)	Writing	Number of Students	Percent (%)	Reading	Number of Students	Percent (%)
No	173	57.67	No	229	76.33	No	177	59.00
Yes	127	42.33	Yes	71	23.67	Yes	123	41.00
Total	300	100.00		300	100.00		300	100.00

Table 5: Summary of the number of developmental courses needed.

Developmental Courses Needed	Number of Students	Percent (%)
0	143	47.67
1	54	18.00
2	44	14.67
3	59	19.67
Total	300	100.00

Table 6: Descriptive statistics of the students’ ACCUPLACER scores. N* is the number of missing data points.

Variable	N	N*	Mean	StDev	Variance	Min.	Q1	Median	Q3	Max.
Arithmetic Score	150	150	57.12	30.71	943.34	10	28	47	84.25	118
Elementary Algebra Score	74	226	67.3	23.87	569.72	5	48.5	65	88.5	114
College Math Score	21	279	38.38	18.72	350.55	20	25	31	54	73
Writing Score	296	4	60.17	28.82	830.82	0	30	50	90	90
Sentence Score	146	154	70.61	20.06	402.34	6	56	69	85	115
Reading Score	147	153	61.95	21.99	483.73	6	42	63	80	109

3.3 Student Outcome Classification

The National Student Clearinghouse Student Tracker provided records used to verify college enrollment for program participants. StudentTracker is the only nationwide source of college enrollment and degree data. More than 3,700 colleges and universities — enrolling over 99 percent of all students in public and private U.S. institutions — regularly provide enrollment and graduation data to the Clearinghouse. (National Student Clearinghouse, 2023) Onward students sign a FERPA form allowing the organization access to their enrollment data.

Enrollment data was analyzed to classify successful/unsuccessful outcomes for Onward community college students. Successful outcomes were defined as: 1) Earning an associate’s and/or bachelor’s degree,

or 2) Still enrolled within the 150% normal time to earn a degree (3 years for associates, 6 years for bachelors). Unsuccessful outcomes were defined as: 1) Stopping out (stopped attending college, but did not officially withdraw), 2) Withdrew, or 3) Still enrolled after the 150% normal time to earn a degree. Tables 7 through 9 summarize outcomes by sex, race/ethnicity, and first-generation status.

Table 7: Summary of student outcomes by sex.

Outcomes	Female	Percent (%)	Male	Percent (%)	Unknown	Percent (%)	Total
Unsuccessful	75	49.020	90	61.64	1	100.00	166
Successful	78	50.980	56	38.36	0	0.00	134
Total	153	100.000	146	100.00	1	100.00	300

Table 8: Summary of student outcomes by race/ethnicity.

Outcome	American Indian/Alaska Native	Asian	Black or African American	Hispanic or Latino	Other	Two or More Races	Unknown	White	Total
Unsuccessful	1	4	33	93	3	11	10	11	166
Successful	2	4	23	85	3	6	4	7	134
Total	3	8	56	178	6	17	14	18	300

Table 9: Summary of student outcomes by first-generation status. First-generation college student, which for Rhode Island GEAR UP is defined as "no parent living in the household has a four-year college degree from any US state."

Outcome	Non-First-Generation	Percent (%)	First-Generation	Percent (%)	Total
Unsuccessful	42	48.84	124	57.94	166
Successful	44	51.16	90	42.06	134
Total	86	100.00	214	100.00	300

3.4 Analytical Methods

3.4.1 Multiple Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is the most popular model for binary outcome data. The general logistic regression model has multiple explanatory variables that can be quantitative, categorical, or both. For p explanatory variables, the model for the log odds is

$$\text{logit}[P(Y = 1)] = \alpha + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_p x_p. \quad (1)$$

The parameter β_j refers to the effect of x_j on the log odds that $Y=1$, adjusting for the other x 's. For example, $\exp(\beta_1)$ is the multiplicative effect on the odds of a 1-unit increase in x_1 , at a fixed value for $\beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_px_p$, such as when x_2, \dots, x_p is held constant. (Agresti, 2019)

The corresponding formula for $P(Y=1)$ using the exponential function $\exp(\alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_px_p) = e^{(\alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_px_p)}$,

$$p = \frac{\exp(\alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_px_p)}{1 + \exp(\alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_px_p)} \quad (2)$$

The effect parameter β determines the rate of increase or decrease of the curve for $P(Y=1)$. The sign of β indicates whether the curve ascends ($\beta > 0$) or descends ($\beta < 0$). When $\beta = 0$, the curve flattens to a horizontal straight line and the binary response variable is independent of the explanatory variable. (Agresti, 2019)

3.4.2 Variable Selection

The purposeful selection method process proposed by Hosmer, et. al. (2000) was used to build the model for this analysis. The first step was to construct an initial main-effects model using explanatory variables that include known important variables and others that may show evidence of being relevant when used as sole predictors (e.g., having p-value < 0.2).

Backward elimination was conducted, keeping a variable if it is either significant at a somewhat more stringent level or shows evidence of being a relevant confounder, in the sense that the estimated effect of a key variable changes substantially when it is removed. (Hosmer, et. al. 2000)

Variables were then added to the model that were not included in the first step but were significant when adjusting for the variables in the model after backward selection. These variables were not significantly associated with the outcomes but may make an important contribution in the presence of the other variables. However, this was not the case.

Interactions among the variables were checked using significance levels of 0.05 and 0.01. These tests showed that there were no significant interactions between the variables. Diagnostics were run to check for overall model fit. The test statistic is the difference between the residual deviance for the model with predictors and the null model and is distributed chi-squared with degrees of freedom equal to the differences in degrees of freedom between the current and the null model (i.e., the number of predictor variables in the model). (Hosmer, et. al. 2000)

3.4.3 Goodness of Fit Tests

Several goodness of fit tests were used to assess model fit. The first being deviance. Deviance evaluates the significance of the overall model. This test asks whether the model with predictors fits significantly better than the full model. The test statistic is the difference between the residual deviance for the model with predictors and the full model. The test statistic is a distributed chi-squared with

degrees of freedom equal to the differences in degrees of freedom between the current and the null model (i.e., the number of predictor variables in the model).

Second, the Pearson goodness-of-fit was used to assess the discrepancy between the current model and the full model. A well-fitted model should have the values of the Pearson statistic and the residual degrees of freedom closely the same. The closer the value, the better the fit. With a p-value > 0.05, the Pearson Goodness of Fit test indicates the hypothesis of the model not well-fitted can be rejected. The test can be used to support the acceptance of the model. (Hilbe, 2016)

The Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test was also used to compare the observed and expected or predicted probabilities as categorized across levels of predicted values. The predicted probabilities of the model are divided into a specific number of groups. The range of predicted probabilities is collapsed into groups of probabilities. Each group has a range of probabilities. The number of successes and failures are calculated for each group and compared to the probabilities for each group. The absolute differences are summed, resulting in the Hosmer-Lemeshow statistic. The degrees of freedom are the number of groups less two. P-values greater than 0.05 indicate a well-fitted model. One rejects the null hypothesis that observed and predicted probabilities are the same. (Hilbe, 2016)

3.4.4 Odds of Success and Odds Ratio

The multiple logistic regression model above indicates that the logit increases by β for every 1-unit increase in x when the other variables are held at a fixed value. Exponentiating both sides of the multiple logistic regression model give an interpretation of the odds and odds ratio. The odds of success are:

$$\frac{\hat{\pi}}{1 - \hat{\pi}} = \exp(\alpha + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_p x_p) \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the odds multiply by e^β for every c-unit increase in x . (Agresti, 2019, Bilder and Loughin, 2015)

To determine how the odds of success have changed by this c-unit increase, the odds ratio is:

$$\theta = \frac{\exp(\alpha + \beta_{x+c})}{\exp(\alpha + \beta x)} = \exp(c\beta) \quad (4)$$

The standard interpretation of this odds ratio is the odds of a success change by $\exp(c\beta)$ times for every c-unit increase in x when the other variables are held at a fixed value. (Bilder and Loughin, 2015)

3.4.5 Statistical Inference: Wald and Likelihood Ratio Tests

Hypothesis tests can be used to assess the importance of explanatory variables in a model. A test of $H_o: \beta = 0$ vs $H_a: \beta \neq 0$ evaluates the explanatory term in the logistic regression model above. If $\beta = 0$, the corresponding explanatory term is excluded from the model. If $\beta \neq 0$, the corresponding term is included in the model. A Wald test or Likelihood ratio test is used to evaluate β . (Bilder and Loughin, 2015)

The Wald statistic is:

$$Z_o = \frac{\hat{\beta}}{SE} \quad (5)$$

where SE is the unrestricted standard error of $\hat{\beta}$. If the null hypothesis is true, Z_o has an approximate normal standard distribution. The confidence interval for the Wald statistic is:

$$\hat{\beta} \pm z_{\frac{\alpha}{2}}(SE) \quad (6)$$

The p-value is defined as:

$$2P(Z > |Z_o|) \quad (7)$$

where Z has a standard normal distribution. (Agresti, 2019, Bilder and Loughin, 2015)

The Likelihood ratio test statistic equals:

$$2 \log \left(\frac{l_1}{l_0} \right) = 2[\log(l_1) - \log(l_0)] = 2(L_1 - L_0) \quad (8)$$

where L_0 and L_1 denote the maximized log-likelihood functions. The maximized value of the likelihood function by l_0 under $H_o: \beta=0$ and by l_1 when β need not equal zero. The likelihood ratio statistic can be informally written as:

$$\Lambda = \frac{\text{Maximum of likelihood function under } H_o}{\text{Maximum of likelihood function under } H_o \text{ or } H_a} \quad (9)$$

(Agresti, 2019, Bilder and Loughin, 2015)

4. Results

Casual studies of remediation have shown that developmental education has negative impacts on college-level course completion and credit accrual for students and inhibit student success. Many students referred to developmental education do not go on to complete college level courses. (Community College Research Center, 2021) Results described herein focus on the relationship between student outcomes at community college and developmental coursework. The multiple logistic regression model results show that student outcomes are negatively affected by developmental coursework.

4.1 Multiple Logistic Regression Model

The first step in creating the multiple logistic regression model was to apply Hosmer, et. al's (2000) approach to purposeful selection of variables where several iterations of statistical model were run using each variable as a sole predictor. Table 10 summarizes the results of the selection process.

Table 10: Variables deemed relevant during the first part of the selection process. A p-value of 0.2 was used to determine if the variable was relevant to the analysis.

Variable	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
Developmental Courses Needed	-0.3432	0.1029	-3.3360	0.0009
Sex	-0.5004	0.2344	-2.1350	0.0328
Developmental Math Course	-0.6579	0.2399	-2.7420	0.0061
Developmental Reading Course	-0.7359	0.2425	-3.0350	0.0024
Developmental Writing Course	-0.7571	0.2887	-2.6230	0.0087
Pell Grant Recipient	0.9109	0.2868	3.1760	0.0015
ACCUPLACER College Math	0.9746	0.4784	2.0370	0.0417

Backward elimination was then applied resulting in the final model:

$$\text{logit}[P(Y = 1)] = 0.4238 - 0.3600x_1 - 5580x_2 \quad (10)$$

where x_1 = Number of Developmental Courses Needed and x_2 = Sex (M = 1, F = 0).

The summary of the multiple logistic regression model output is provided in Table 11 below.

Table 11. A summary of the multiple logistic output.

Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
Intercept	0.4238	0.2004	2.1150	0.0344
Developmental Courses Needed	-0.3600	0.1045	-3.4470	0.0006
Sex (M=1, F=0)	-0.5580	0.2404	-2.3210	0.0203

4.2 Goodness of Fit

Goodness of fit tests assess the discrepancy between the current model and the full model. If the p-value for the goodness-of-fit test is lower than your chosen significance level, the predicted probabilities deviate from the observed probabilities in a way that the binomial distribution does not predict. Table 13 shows that the Deviance test indicates a poor model fit, while the Pearson and Hosmer-Lemeshow tests indicate a good model fit with p-values over 0.05.

Table 13: Summary of goodness of fit.

Goodness-of-Fit Test	DF	Chi-Square	P-Value
Deviance	297	395.37	0.000
Pearson	297	299.93	0.441
Hosmer-Lemeshow	3	0.46	0.928

4.2 Wald and Likelihood Test

The summary of the analysis of variance output is provided in Table 12 and shows that the predictors Developmental Courses Needed and Sex have a statistically significant relationship with a successful outcome at community college at the 95% significance level.

Table 12: A summary of the analysis of variance output.

Variables	LR Chisq	Wald Test	
		Df	Pr(>Chisq)
Developmental Courses Needed	12.5012	1	0.0004
Sex	5.4564	1	0.0195

4.3 Odds Ratios

The odds ratios indicate that community college students are 30% less likely to have a successful outcome at community college if they need to take developmental courses. This means that each additional developmental course needed is associated with a 30% decrease in the odds of having a successful outcome at community college when sex is held at a fixed value. The odds ratios also indicate that male students are 43% less likely to have a successful outcome at community college when the developmental courses needed is held at a fixed value. Table 14 is the summary of the odds ratios.

Table 14: Odds ratios and 95% confidence intervals for developmental courses needed and sex.

Variables	Odds Ratio	Lower 95% C.I.	Upper 95% C.I.
Intercept	1.5278	1.0351	2.2748
Developmental Courses Needed	0.6976	0.5661	0.8534
Sex	0.5724	0.3559	0.9145

4.4 Estimated Probability

The estimated probability of a successful outcome at community college is:

$$\hat{\pi}(x) = \frac{\exp(0.4238 - 0.3600x_1 - 0.5580x_2)}{1 + \exp(0.4238 - 0.3600x_1 - 0.5580x_2)} \quad (11)$$

where x_1 = Number of Developmental Courses Needed and x_2 = Sex (M = 1, F = 0).

Since β_1 and β_2 are negative, this indicates that the estimated probabilities will decrease with each developmental course that is needed. The estimated probability of a successful outcome at community college can be seen in Table 15 below.

Table 15: Estimated probability of a successful outcome at a community college based on the number of developmental courses needed and sex.

Number of Developmental Courses Needed	Males $\hat{\pi}(x)$	Females $\hat{\pi}(x)$
0	0.4665	0.6044
1	0.3789	0.5159
2	0.2985	0.4265

Overall, male students have a lower probability of a successful outcome from community college than females regardless of the number of developmental courses needed. For example, male students that needed to take 3 developmental courses have a 0.2289 or 22.89% probability of a successful outcome at community college whereas female students have a 0.3416 or 34.16% probability of a successful outcome.

5. Discussion

The overall objective of this study was to examine the relationship between developmental coursework and successful outcomes at community college. Results show that the number of developmental courses needed has a statistically significant negative effect on successful outcomes. Community college students are 30% less likely to have a successful outcome at community college if they need to take developmental courses. Males are more negatively impacted by the number of developmental courses needed than females. Results show that male students are 43% less likely to have a successful outcome at community college when the number of developmental courses needed is held at a fixed value. A report from the National Center for Education Statistics (2016) states that remedial course taking increases the requirements students need to complete before taking college-level courses, prolonging time to degree, potentially hindering transfer, and completion.

5.1 Relationship Between Developmental Coursework and Successful Outcomes

Many incoming college students are deemed underprepared for the rigor of college-level study, and they are referred to remedial courses (or developmental education). Up to 65% of community college students take at least one remedial course within six years of initial enrollment. (Ran and Lin, 2022). More than half of Onward We Learn students need to take one or more developmental courses at community college. The questions that need to be answered are: 1. Why is this happening? and 2. What can be done to prevent it?

Some students may have learned math successfully but scored poorly on the placement test. Other students may have never learned the high school math being assessed, while others failed to learn the material. Some students may be immigrants who had trouble understanding the English used in the math test. (CRCC, 2009) Each student is different, and their individual needs must be assessed to ensure a successful outcome from community college.

A report published in 2016 by the U.S. Department of Education, National Center for Education Statistics discusses that higher proportions of Black and Hispanic students, first-generation students, and those from low-income backgrounds participate in developmental coursework than do their peers. Onward We Learn students are low-income (based on free/reduced price lunch status at the time of enrollment), 95% identify as students of color, and approximately 93% are first-generation students. The relationship discussed in the report was evident for our students with more than half having to take one or more developmental courses. We hope this research will assist in creating interventions and academic enrichment programs to prevent our students from being placed in developmental courses at community college and set them up for success.

5.2 Limitations of Study

This study had several limitations. The first being the number of data points available for analysis. Onward We Learn did not have access to all student data. Though students signed a Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act (FERPA) form, Onward We Learn had limited access to student data. The data did not contain

specific developmental course information, such as course name and grade earned. The logistic regression model may have fit better if this information was included in the analysis. Perhaps, this information would have been a better indicator of the student outcomes than the number of courses the student took. Knowing whether the student completed the developmental course would have also been beneficial for a better fitting model.

Second, the sample size was small. Three hundred (300) students were part of the analysis but there were more. Not all students agree to sign a FERPA form allowing Onward We Learn access to their academic data which limited the number of students in the analysis. Each year at least 30% (approximately 100 students) of Onward We Learn students attend the local community college. This study contained four cohorts of students. Therefore, the sample should have contained 400 or more students. Though the model was statistically significant at the 95% significance level, more data points would have provided a better model fit.

Finally, the sample was not random. Students that enroll in Onward We Learn must meet one or both of the following requirements: eligible for free/reduced lunch and/or be a first-generation college student. Race/ethnicity was not added to the logistic regression model because the sample is 59% Hispanic or Latino. This resulted in race/ethnicity not being statistically significant.

5.3 Future Work

College remediation is a widespread practice in U.S. public higher education. Each year, millions of students are required to take developmental courses before they move on to credit-bearing college-level coursework. A report published in 2016 by the U.S. Department of Education, National Center for Education Statistics states that national data indicates that nearly 70 percent of students beginning at community colleges took at least one developmental course during their undergraduate studies. Further work is needed to identify the underlying issues that can hinder a successful outcome at community college.

Future work may include investigating if the sequence of developmental courses recommended by the community college were completed and completed successfully. Twenty percent of Onward students were required to complete 3 developmental courses during their time at community college. This is a serious problem that can hinder student success. Are grades received in developmental courses an indicator of a successful outcome? Perhaps, student grades can be used as an intervention point by Onward staff, as well as their school advisor to identify a potential issue before it begins.

Does the problem begin before the student begins their college career? Further research needs to be done to identify intervention points throughout high school to make sure the student is on track with mathematics, reading, and writing. Onward We Learn does a good job of tracking some of these major points by meeting annual targets required for the GEAR UP grant. Math course taking, English Language Arts proficiency, and math proficiency are all tracked for the federal grant. Frequent check-ins with students and staff would ensure students are on track. Currently, Onward We Learn has developed learning strands to assess the math and writing needs of our students. The diagnostic test results from these programs will be beneficial for any future work.

Understanding major obstacles can help community colleges better identify struggling students, design strategies to help them overcome obstacles, and make developmental coursework more effective in retaining students and enabling them to progress to college-level coursework. (NCES, 2016) While this study had numerous limitations and there is much future work needed, this preliminary study does indicate that developmental coursework has a negative impact of a successful outcome at community college. All

relevant stakeholders should take note of the number of developmental courses our students need to take and provide guidance to ensure college access and completion.

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